
CORPORATE LEARNING STRATEGIES AND EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION

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Abstract: *The study examined corporate learning strategies and employee satisfaction. The study determined the impact of embedded systems, empowerment, and systems connection on employee satisfaction. Related literature was reviewed for the objectives of the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. 297 employees from four firms selected from Delta and Edo State. The sample size used for data analysis was 162. The questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. The data collected from the administration of the questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive and inference statistics. All relevant statistical testing was done. The finding of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between embedded systems and employee satisfaction; there is a significant relationship between empowerment and employee satisfaction and there is a significant relationship between systems connections and employee satisfaction. It was concluded that employee satisfaction is a key factor for the success of any organization which can be achieved if the organization encourages embedded systems, employee empowerment and system connection. It was therefore recommended among others that; organizations should endeavour to sustain the habit of measuring gaps between current and expected performance and make lessons learned available to all employees and contribute to knowledge.*

Keywords: Corporate learning strategies, employee satisfaction, embedded systems, empowerment system connection

Introduction

The elements involved in embedding employees in their jobs are: links, fit and sacrifice. These are associated with where employees work and where they reside. As a retention construct, embedded system decreases employees' turnover intentions and actual voluntary turnover (Ampofo, Coetzer & Poisat, 2017). Andika and Darmanto (2020) opined that, when employees are newly hired, organization's culture are emphasized during their first weeks of training. Employers are required to understand employee's interests and hobbies and connect them with employees who may already be involved in similar interests and hobbies. These new employees will feel like they belong, even if it is their first week at work. But when employees are not new, it is the responsibility of employers to check to discuss career goals, any potential issues at work, or any struggles they are facing outside of work. This gives employees hope and job satisfaction (Tampi, Nabella & Sari, 2022).

Empowerment is the constant process of giving employees with the necessary skills, training, resources, encouragement, and incentive to achieve at their best (Yin, Wang, & Lu, 2019). Empowerment is vital

because it promotes employee satisfaction, resulting in happier and more loyal employees. The truth is that empowerment is more than a single act or process; it is a corporate culture and the structure of the organization (Lasspied, Awad, & Giorat, 2020). Empowerment leads to employee satisfaction by providing employees with a sense of independence, creativity, and control over their schedule. Employee satisfaction is an intangible yet strong force that fosters a more engaged and productive workplace. Satisfied employees are more likely to do their tasks well and for much longer. According to Jonathan (2023), not all organizations have caught up to the changing needs of their workforce, **65% of employees** are satisfied with their current jobs. He further said that 51% of employees are disengaged, while 13% are actively disengaged. Only 36% count themselves as engaged (Jonathan, 2023; Paais, Pattiruhu, 2020). Empowered workers are happy and have the ability to promote good change throughout the firm. Changing how employees see their function and discuss it with their colleagues may result in more productive and loyal teams. Connecting with employees' needs and wishes and facilitating communication can not only improve employee culture and morale, but also have a major influence on retention and organizational success (Hulshof, Demerouti, & Le-Blanc, 2020).

System connection is another area to be considered when talking about employee satisfaction. Employees with strong personal ties to a firm are more likely to be satisfied at work, and less likely to leave. These new and existing employees build a local network outside of work and at work. According to Choi (2020), it is a good act to pair each new employee with a buddy to help them make friends during the first few weeks. Organizations can organize lunches, happy hours, or other social events with colleagues to help new employees get to know the office. To set up lasting relationships, companies should also give each new employee a mentor, whom they can get to know, learn from, and rely on. These mentors will not only be able to help their mentees make friends, but they will be able to tell early if the new employee is struggling or not (Bekirogullari, 2019).

One of the ways organization can satisfy employees is to encourage embeddedness, empowerment and system connection among others (Firzli, 2018). It is important for organizations to create a supportive learning environment. Every company suffers from employee turnover. Especially when losing a particularly talented employee, managers are often faced with the question on how to prevent this in the future (Quested, Thøgersen-Ntoumani,

Uren, Hard castle & Ryan, 2018). Apart from the many well-known measures of employee retention, there are also other factors you can take into account when trying to keep your talent from leaving. A relevant, effective, yet rather unknown factor is employee embeddedness. Base on the aforementioned, this study examined impact of embedded system, empowerment and systems connection on employee satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem

Embeddedness is a measure of employee engagement which has a huge impact on employee satisfaction. If an employee does not feel connected to the organization, it results in dissatisfaction. This implied that for an employee to be satisfied, he/she must be fit to do the job, link with friends and

colleagues and make sacrifices for the organization by working judiciously. Considering the above, organizations and management should pay attention to embeddedness in employees. Organizations are to integrate employees into processes and culture. While doing this, empowerment should not be left out. An empowered employee gives more to the organization by increasing productivity and performance. Companies, whose employees are not embedded, empowered and connected, are liable to suffer setbacks. They might not be competitive, successful, and productive. Thus, the current examined impact of embedded system, empowerment, and systems connection on employee satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study

- Determine the impact of the embedded system on employee satisfaction.
- Evaluate the impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction.
- Assess the impact of systems connection on employee satisfaction.

Research Questions

- ❖ Determine the impact of the embedded system on employee satisfaction.
- ❖ Evaluate the impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction.
- ❖ Assess the impact of systems connection on employee satisfaction.

Hypotheses of the Study

- Ho₁: There is no significant impact of embedded systems on employee satisfaction.
Ho₂: There is no significant impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction.
Ho₃: There is no significant impact of systems connection on employee satisfaction.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Embedded System

Embeddedness is a measure of employee engagement which goes beyond what happens in the office, but it nevertheless has a huge impact on employee satisfaction, particularly for new employees. If an employee doesn't feel connected to the community he or she lives and works in, the likelihood they will leave increases exponentially (Waterschoot, Kaap-Deeder & Vansteenkiste, 2020). Embeddedness is broken down into three elements (Waterschoot et al., 2020): (1) Fit.-the employee feels like they belong at the company and in their community. They feel like they share the same values and goals, and they believe they can contribute meaningfully. (2) Links- employees are connected; they have strong relationships at work as well as friends outside of work. They feel invested in their local network. (3) Sacrifice- If employees were to leave organization, they would feel as though they were giving something up such as projects at work, meaningful friendships, or a promising career path. The consequences of leaving are greater than the promise of new opportunities elsewhere. Ampofo, Coetzer and Poisat (2017) recommend employers should pay attention to embeddedness in employees. If embeddedness is an issue, he suggests firms should improve their boarding process. Assessing embeddedness should not

only occur once an employee joins an organization. It should be an integral part of a firm's ongoing efforts to engage employees. Companies can take steps to address each component above (Jallad, 2021).

Empowerment

Empowerment refers to people's level of autonomy and self-determination at work. This allows people to represent their interests in a responsible and self-determined manner while acting on their authority. It is the process of getting stronger and more confident, particularly in managing one's own life and asserting one's rights. Empowerment also refers to professional support that helps individuals overcome their feelings of helplessness and lack of influence, as well as identify and apply their skills to execute their jobs (Jallad, 2021). In the workplace, empowerment is a realistic method to resource-based intervention. Empowerment is viewed as a method for increasing employee responsibility. Empowerment is a significant notion in discussions about increasing employee engagement and happiness (Ulutas, 2018). Empowerment, defined as a shift from a deficit-oriented to a more strength-oriented perspective, is increasingly appearing in management ideas, as well as continuing education and self-help (Rahmi, Achmad, & Adhimursandi, 2020).

System Connections

An employee connects successfully with the company when they feel needed at work, do not have to pretend to be someone else, and totally identify with the business's aims and vision (Rahmi et al., 2020). Employees will consider sticking with their present employer if the connections both outside and inside the company benefit them. System connection entails reciprocal praise, honest feedback, and the encouragement of mutual improvement. There should be an interaction between employers and employees. The employers would need to set a positive example. Only managers who express gratitude to their staff and are prepared to establish important social connections with their team may expect the same in return (Behbahani, 2023).

The pace at which one employee connects with the organization is influenced by the connection of the entire group. If a new employee finds that there are few individuals hanging out at the, it instantly indicates a lack of social bonds among employees. Also, if employees see that their coworkers are looking for new employment. Naturally, they will question why this is the case. Regardless matter how happy the employees are, their colleagues' bad emotional state of mind will have an indirect impact on their own well-being. Thus, these signals have the potential to emotionally disengage personnel inside the firm (Behbahani, 2023).

Employee Satisfaction

Satisfied employees are critical to the health of your company. An employee who enjoys their job will work harder and stay with the company longer, so creating a space of positivity and respect in the workplace can contribute to the company's success. Employees want jobs they will not dread. They want to work in a healthy environment with friendly management and colleagues, do meaningful work, and get paid well. A business prioritizes employees' satisfaction, and reap considerable benefits such as lower turnover, higher productivity, positive organization culture, and loyalty, According to Steben

(2023), 20 per cent of employees feel satisfied and engaged at work, and if employees are satisfied, they work diligently (Steben, 2023).

Impact of Embedded Systems on Employee Satisfaction

Employee embeddedness is about having employees feel anchored in the organization's culture rather than merely incorporated into it. This means that the employer must examine not only compensation, well-being, and empowerment, but also how to establish an atmosphere in which people desire to stay, mostly because leaving would force them to give up too much. This environment would inevitably contain a strong social network both within and outside of the office, a strong personal and organizational fit, and a strong interdependence between the firm and its workforce. Embedded systems provide mechanisms to monitor the difference between present and expected performance, make lessons learned available to all employees, and track the effectiveness of training time and resources (Ampofo, Coetzer, & Poisat, 2017).

Impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction

Empowered employees increased their confidence degree and self-reliance. This extra confidence creates job satisfaction and increases levels of productivity. Empowerment encompasses the enlargement of an employee's job duties by giving them the (Bekirogullari, 2019) independence and authority of decision-making about their job without the approval of his immediate supervisor; it is the level of responsibility and authority given to an employee; motivate employees enthusiast to utilize their skills, abilities and creativity by accepting accountability for their work; it enables employees training, provided with all the appropriate and relevant information and the best possible tools. Empowerment helps to recognize people for taking initiative, gives people control over the resources they need to accomplish their work, and supports employees who take calculated risks (Choi, 2020; Lassoued et al., 2020).

Impact of systems connection on employee satisfaction

Employees will contemplate leaving their positions if their relationships (social ties) both inside and outside of the organization lose value or do not exist at all. Valuable social links extend beyond the well-known; I get along with my colleagues at work. They include reciprocal praise, honest feedback, and the encouragement of mutual development. Managers set a good example in this regard and take the initiative to build these relationships. Only managers who express gratitude to their staff and are prepared to create significant social relationships with their team can expect to receive the same in return.

Employees' commitment to their jobs benefits not just them, but also their employers. According to Behbahan (2023), employees' connection to their work has the biggest influence on total job satisfaction and performance. He went on to define Employee Connection as a sense of belonging in the workplace based on several aspects of employee experience, including (1) connection to work: having a sense of satisfaction and purpose daily; (2) connection to people: developing relationships with peers,

teams, managers, and leaders; and (3) connection to culture: feeling that personal values align with the culture, mission, values, and norms.

System connection helps individuals to think globally, collaborate with the outside world to satisfy shared needs, and seek solutions from across the company when addressing challenges (Behbahan, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical Framework According to the literature, embedded systems, empowerment, and system connections are associated with employee satisfaction. Thus, fig. 1 below depicts the I below depict the theoretical framework of this study.

Fig. 1: Theoretical Framework of the Study

Source: Researcher, 2024

The above figure indicates the independent variables as embedded system, empowerment, and systems connections while employee satisfaction is the dependent variable. Organizations that encourage embedded systems, empowerment and systems connection make employees happier which makes them (employees) satisfied with their jobs. This satisfaction leads to people helping each other learn, people are given time to support learning, people are rewarded for learning, open and honest feedback, sharing ideas & views, increased trust & transparency, increased performance, increased productivity, employee retention, and customer satisfaction.

Empirical Review

Jallad (2021) examined the relationship between learning organization and job satisfaction from the perspective of the staff of Tulkarem Municipality – Palestine. The study used seven independent variables: continuous learning, inquiry and dialogue, team learning, embedded system, empowerment, system connection, strategic leadership, and their effect on job satisfaction. The study uses a survey to test the hypotheses and answer the study questions, as this kind of data collation is more convenient than other methods. The findings from multiple regression tests revealed that there was a statistically significant impact of strategic leadership and continuous learning on job satisfaction. The recommendations were that managers could build programs and systems to encourage learning at all levels,

Ampofo et al. (2017) responded to calls for further job embeddedness research in a wider range of national, cultural, and organisational contexts. There is a paucity of research on job embeddedness in Thailand and in smaller enterprises. Data collected from 181 employees in small and medium-sized enterprises located in two provinces of Thailand were analysed. Results suggest that organisation embeddedness, but not community embeddedness, predicts turnover intentions in the sample studied. Only a handful of studies have examined the three sub-dimensions of organisation embeddedness: links, fit and sacrifice. Our results showed that each of these sub-dimensions was significantly and negatively associated with turnover intentions. Practical implications of the results and directions for future research are outlined in the paper.

Ulutaş (2018) studied the relationship between job satisfaction and empowerment can be omitted. In this context, a survey was conducted on the employees of 19 different companies operating in different sectors in the Konya Industrial Zone, including the first five hundred and the second five hundred largest industrial establishments in Turkey, and important data on the relationship between empowerment and job satisfaction were reached. According to this research results; It shows that there is a positive relationship between empowerment and job satisfaction.

Alshemmari (2023) investigated the role of employee empowerment (Delegation, Engagement, Trust, Communication and Motivation) in increasing efficiency of employee performance within State Audit Bureau of Kuwait. For that sake, quantitative methodology was employed, and (243) questionnaires were distributed on a sample from human resource department in State Audit Bureau of Kuwait. SPSS was used to tackle and analyze gathered primary data; results of study indicated the acceptance of the main hypothesis which argued that employee empowerment has the ability to increase efficiency of employee performance with $R= 0.901$ and explaining 81.1% of the variance. Study recommended providing career development opportunities and giving employees the chance to take on new responsibilities, take on special projects and participate in professional development courses. Also, arrange for employees to participate in exchanges or internships at other audit bureaus to obtain new perspectives and broaden their experiences. Further recommendations were presented in the study. The study had both practical and theoretical implications, as for practical implications, the study revealed that empowered employees tend to be more engaged, motivated, and committed to their work. As a result, they may perform their job duties with greater efficiency and effectiveness, leading to improved productivity and quality of work. As for the theoretical implications, it was seen through the study that investigating the relationship between employee empowerment and performance can provide insights into social exchange theory, which suggests that employees who feel valued and empowered are more likely to reciprocate with high levels of performance and commitment. As a theoretical contribution, the study revealed that empowerment is a key component of self-determination theory, which suggests that individuals are motivated by a desire to fulfil their basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Investigating the relationship between empowerment and performance can help to further understand this theory and how it can be

applied in the workplace. The practical contribution saw that empowered employees tend to be more engaged, motivated, and committed to their work. As a result, they may perform their job duties with greater efficiency and effectiveness, leading to improved productivity and quality of work.

Tools and Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The target population comprised all employees of Vintex Aluminum Asaba (80), Life Flour Mill Sapele (76), Differential Aluminum (52) and Nelux Paint Benin (89), which made up of 297 employees. The sample size of the study was 170 which was derived from the total population via Taro Yamane (1967) Formula. The four firms were chosen through the random balloting technique. The questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection which was constructed based on the modified Likert 5-point scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The research instrument was face and content validated. The reliability of the instrument was established using the test and retest method with a coefficient of reliability of 0.82 using Cronbach Alpha in SPSS 25. The researcher personally administered copies of the questionnaires to the respondents after due permission from the managers of the respective organizations. 170 copies were distributed but 162 were retrieved which showed a 95% retrieval rate. This is because some of the filled questionnaires were lost, some were not properly filled in, and some of the respondents did not return their copies.

The data collected from the administration of the questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive and inference statistics. The research questions were answered using simple percentages and mean. The formula is as follows:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{5+4+3+2+1}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3.0$$

The mean response that is greater than 3.0 was conserved as Agreed, a mean response that is lesser than 3.0 was considered as Disagreed, while a mean response that is equal to 3.0 was considered as neutral point.

The hypotheses were tested using multiple regressions via SPSS 25 at a significant level of 0.05. The model of multiple regressions is as follows:

Model Specification Using Multiple Regressions

Mathematically, it can be represented as;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EM_1 + \beta_2 EP_2 + \beta_3 SC_3 + E_3 \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

$$ES = f(EM, EP, SC)$$

i. $ES = f(EM)$

$$ES = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EM_1 + E_i \dots (i)$$

Where,

ES = Employee Satisfaction

EM = Embedded System

EP = Empowerment

SC = System Connections
 i = Individual Respondents
 β_0 = Constant Term
 β_i = Regression Coefficient
 E_i = Error Term

ii. $ES = f(EP)$
 $ES = \beta_0 + \beta_2EP_2 + E_2 \dots$ (ii)
 Where,
 ES = Employee satisfaction
 EP = Empowerment

iii. $ES = f(SC)$
 $ES = \beta_0 + \beta_3SC_3 + E_3 \dots$ (iii)
 Where,
 ES = Employee Satisfaction
 SC = System Connections

Analysis of Data and Interpretation

Frequency Tables were used to present analyzed data. Research Questions were answered using simple percentages and meanwhile the hypotheses were tested using multiple regressions at a significant level of 0.05 in SPSS 25.

Answering of Research Questions

Research Question 1

What is the impact of embedded systems on employee satisfaction?

Table 1: Impact of Embedded System on Employee Satisfaction

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	My organization creates systems to measure gaps between current and expected performance.	90 (56%)	37 (23%)	15 (9%)	10 (6%)	10 (6%)	4.15	34.08	Accepted
2.	My organization makes its lessons learned available to all employees.	60 (37%)	80 (49%)	9 (6%)	7 (4%)	6 (4%)	4.12	35.06	Accepted
3.	My organization measures the results of the time and resources spent on training.	92 (57%)	30 (19%)	5 (3%)	20 (12%)	15 (9%)	4.01	34.52	Accepted
GRAND TOTAL							4.09	34.55	Accepted

Table 1 shows the means responses to items 1 – 3 as; 4.15, 4.12 and 4.01 respectively; with a grand mean and standard deviation of 4.09 ± 34.55 . This means that, with embedded system creates systems to measure gaps between current and expected performance; makes its lessons learned available to all employees and measures the results of the time and resources spent on training.

Research Question 2

What is the impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction?

Table 2: impact of Empowerment on Employee Satisfaction

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	UD	D	SD	MEAN	SD	REMARK
4.	My organization recognizes people for taking initiatives.	70 (43%)	60 (37%)	12 (7%)	10 (6%)	10 (6%)	4.05	29.98	Accepted
5.	My organization gives people control over the resources they need to accomplish their work	70 (43%)	60 (37%)	12 (7%)	10 (6%)	10 (6%)	4.25	29.98	Accepted
6.	My organization supports employees who take calculated risks.	70 (43%)	60 (37%)	12 (7%)	10 (6%)	10 (6%)	3.80	29.98	Accepted
	GRAND TOTAL						4.03	29.44	

Table 2 shows the means responses to items 4 – 6 as; 4.05, 4.25 and 3.80 respectively; with a grand mean and standard deviation of 4.03 ± 29.44 . This means that empowerment helps organizations to: recognize people for taking initiative, gives people control over the resources they need to accomplish their work and supports employees who take calculated risks.

Research Question 3

What is the impact of systems connections on employee satisfaction?

Table 3: impact of Systems Connections on Employee Satisfaction

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	UD	D	SD	MEAN	SD	REMARK
7.	My organization encourages people to think from a global perspective.	60 (37%)	62 (38%)	6 (4%)	18 (11%)	16 (10%)	3.81	26.51	Accepted
8.	My organization works together with the outside community to meet mutual needs.	50 (31%)	100 (62%)	4 (2%)	5 (3%)	3 (2%)	4.17	42.72	Accepted
9.	My organization encourages people to get answers from across the organization when solving problems.	85 (52%)	55 (34%)	5 (3%)	10 (6%)	7 (4%)	4.24	35.97	Accepted
	GRAND TOTAL						4.07	35.07	Accepted

Table 3 shows the mean responses to items 7-9 as; 3.81, 4.17, and 4.24 respectively; with a grand mean and standard deviation of 4.07 ± 35.07 respectively. This means that systems connections encourage people to think from a global perspective; make organizations work together with the outside community

to meet mutual needs and encourage people to get answers from across the organization when solving problems.

Test of Hypotheses

They hypotheses were tested using multiple regressions in SPSS 25. The output of the Analysis is shown in Table 4 – 7 below:

Multiple Regression Model for the study

$$ES = \beta_0 + \beta_1EM + \beta_2EP + \beta_3SC$$

ES = Employee Satisfaction → Dependent Variable

EM (Embedded System), EP (Empowerment) and SC (Systems Connections) → Independent Variables

Table 4: Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	SC, EP, EM ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: ES

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 5: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.899 ^a	.809	.805	.26673	.164

a. Predictors: (Constant), SC, EP, EM

b. Dependent Variable: ES

The R value of 0.899 in the Model Summary Table (Table 5) represents the Pearson correlation. This implies that there is a strong and positive correlation across the variables since the value of r (0.899) tends to 1.

The R Square (r²) value of 0.809 (Table 5) is known as the coefficient of determination. It shows the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. This implies that 81% of the variation in Employee Satisfaction (ES) can be explained by Embedded System (EM), Empowerment (EP) and Systems Connections (SC).

Table 6: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	47.463	3	15.821	222.381	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.241	158	.071		
	Total	58.704	161			

a. Dependent Variable: ES

b. Predictors: (Constant), SC, EP, EM

The value of Sig (0.00) in Table 6 indicates that, the independent variables (EM, EP and SC) combined has a statistically significant association with the dependent variable (ES).

Table 7: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.252	.196		6.398	.000		
	EM	.691	.077	.794	9.016	.000	.156	6.396
	EP	.098	.090	-.069	-1.096	.025	.304	3.291
	SC	.192	.105	.173	1.825	.017	.135	7.397

a. Dependent Variable: ES

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant impact of embedded systems on employee satisfaction.

The Sig-value (0.000) of E) in Table 7 indicates that there is a significant relationship between Embedded Systems (EM) and Employee Satisfaction (ES) since the Sig-value (0.000) is lesser than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant impact of embedded systems on employee satisfaction is rejected. This implies that there is a significant impact of embedded systems on employee satisfaction. In every additional effort to improve Embedded Systems (EM), Employee Satisfaction (ES) is expected to increase by 0.691 (Table 7) assuming other independent variables remain constant.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction.

The Sig-value (0.025) of Empowerment (EP) in Table 7 indicates that there is a significant relationship between Empowerment (EP) and Employee Satisfaction (ES) since the Sig-value (0.025) is lesser than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction is rejected. This implies that there is a significant impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction. In every additional effort to improve Empowerment (EP), Employee Satisfaction (ES) is expected to increase by 0.98 (Table 7) assuming other independent variables remain constant.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant impact of system connections on employee satisfaction.

The Sig-value (0.017) of Systems Connections (SC) in Table 7 indicates that there is a significant relationship between Systems Connections (SC) and Employee Satisfaction (ES) since the Sig-value

(0.017) is less than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant impact of systems connections on employee satisfaction is rejected. This implies that there is a significant impact of empowerment on employee satisfaction. In every additional effort to improve Systems Connections (SC), Employee Satisfaction (ES) is expected to increase by 0.192 (Table 7) assuming other independent variables remain constant.

Findings

The study's findings indicated that there is a substantial association between embedded systems and employee satisfaction, as demonstrated by the answer to research question 1 (Table 1) and the test of hypothesis 1. Embedded systems establish mechanisms to monitor gaps between present and expected performance, make lessons learned available to all employees, and track the effectiveness of training time and money. This discovery is consistent with the findings of Ampofo et al. (2017), who discovered that embedded systems evaluate the differences between present and predicted performance as well as the outcomes of training time and resources.

The response to research question 2 (Table 2), as well as the test of hypothesis 2, demonstrated that there is a substantial association between empowerment and employee happiness. Empowerment enables organizations to recognize individuals for taking initiative, offer workers authority over the resources they require to complete their tasks, and encourage employees who take measured risks. This conclusion complements the findings of Choi (2020) and Lassoued et al. (2020), who believe that empowerment encourages individuals to take initiative and provides them control over the resources they need to complete their tasks.

The answers to research question 3 (Table 3) and the test of hypothesis 3 also demonstrated a substantial association between systems connectivity and employee satisfaction. Systems linkages inspire individuals to think globally; they enable organizations to collaborate with the outside community to satisfy shared requirements; and they motivate people to seek solutions from across the organization when addressing challenges. This conclusion is consistent with the findings of Behbahani (2023), who said that system linkage promotes individuals to think globally, collaborate, and seek answers while addressing difficulties.

Conclusion

Employee happiness is critical to the success of any business; when people are content at work, the emotion spreads across the organization, driving organizational progress. Employee happiness may be increased if the organization promotes embedded systems, employee empowerment, and system integration. This study is consistent with Behbahani's (2023) findings, which said that system connectedness promotes individuals to think globally, collaborate, and seek answers while addressing difficulties.

Recommendation

- Organizations should consistently measure performance gaps and share lessons gained with all workers.
- Stakeholders should reward initiative and encourage staff to take appropriate risks.

➤ Encouraging continuous stakeholder ties fosters global thinking and collaboration with the community to satisfy shared needs.

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